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A Critical Analysis of NEP2020: Promoting Holistic Development through Early Childhood Care and Education

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ABSTRACT

Education ensures the holistic development of an individual, which in turn supports in the development of the country. The paper discusses the value of holistic development and early

childhood education for future mothers. The committee that was established in June 2017 and submitted in its report on May 31, 2019, published NEP 2020. This study focuses on how NEP 2020 promotes early childhood care education. It also evaluates how the new 5+3+3+4 schooling structure contributes to children's holistic development. Activity and investigation are all part of the versatile, multicultural, multidimensional early childhood care education approach. based learning that supports in children's development socio-emotionally and righteously. With eighty-five percent of children seeing continuous cognitive rapid development before the age of six years, the goal of the new education policy (NEP 2020) was to revive the ECCE initiative. Food and Nutrition, physical well-being, sociable about, cognitive, ethical emotional, physical, and aesthetic qualities are all included in ECCE. The method applied in this paper was qualitative. Anganwadi is the name for village childcare centers located throughout India. Children at ECCE engage with educational endeavours knowingly, respectfully, and with liberty.

KEYWORDS: ECCE, Holistic Development, National Education Policy 2020, School Education.

Introduction:

The stage that is most important for the development of the human mind is thought to be the early years, which can be described as between the ages of 0 to 8. The field of neuroscience reveals strong evidence that "every year cerebral growth based on learning creates cognitive and cellular connections affecting behaviour, cognition, and well-being continuously" (Muttar 2007;40). ECCE which has developed globally significance to comprehend the strong and complete development of young learners, has taken care of this time of a child's life all over the globe. ECCE is an emerging idea. Sarva Shiksha Abhyan (2000) emphasized the value of ECCE, believing that no child should be ignored until they are completed elementary education. Previous to the national education policy becoming set up in 1986. "The state shall endeavour to furnish all children with Early childhood care and Education until they exceed the age of six years." The Indian Constitution's article 45 was updated in 2002 to add a period leading basic education, enhancing the basis for development on all levels. Toddlers need to be given the opportunities and manifestations that are necessary to their overall development. In besides opportunities for expressing himself, perception, and social interaction, ECCE must include activities that make use of neighbourhood assets for creative work, games, dancing, performing, and other forms of creativity.

Concept of Child-Care and Education:

The child care facility providers interact with both individual children and small groups of children on a daily basis. In order to meet the child as an individual and help with meeting their needs, he or she tries to consider the child's viewpoint. E.g, a 4-year-old kid snatches the hand of a child caregiver. He understands that the child wants to see the vibrant birds on the

playing field. We refer to these educational efforts as caring. The child and the child care caregivers may discuss certain values and customs in this transaction, such as the need to respect and not frighten or upset coloured birds, or the child may simply receive grateful treatment, both of which have an influence on the child and ultimately help in the development of particular norms and values. We are concerned about such developmental experiences. The kids and their childcare provider share information at the same time. As they watch the vibrant birds, they explore things like their given names and nutrition. Through the child's own activities, he or she will likely adapt knowledge and customs about birds, or in other words, learn a certain thing. This is because the activity enables for the adaptation of novel information and abilities that we refer to as the child-care workers' job (care, teaching and bringing up).

Figure1, Early Childhood Care and Education

Review of the Related Literature:

The affect of government policies and evidence-based initiatives on the influence of early childhood NEP 2020 replaces the currently 34-year-old National Policy on Education (NPE 1968) by upgrading the 10+2 framework of the school curriculum with a 5+3+3+4 structure that focuses on Early Childhood Care and Education. The revealed age range of 3 to 6 years in NPE is introduced as an essential pedagogy in NEP 2020 to develop the pre-natal age of children from every socioeconomic strata. This unique strategy aims to benefit those in developing and underprivileged sectors of society. Kalyani et al. (2020) have documented the impact of NEP 2020's four challenges—quality, equity, and affordability, accountability, and access—on the appropriate stakeholders—students, educators, and the parents.

A four-year B.Ed. program and Teachers Eligibility Test (TET) certificate will be the basic requirements for Government teacher recruitments, according to NEP 2020. This will make it possible to recruit qualified employees to change the preschool learning program's effectiveness. The impact of preschool education was examined by Pianta et al. (2009) in relation to the function of evidence-based approaches and government initiatives. Through research and experimental methodologies, the results of investigations were carried out from the helping hand, elementary school, and child care programs. Research indicates that preschool programs have a sustainable beneficial effect on young children's development in

social and cognitive areas. It also involves a search. Pre-schoolers' social conduct may be adversely affected by minor testimony, but this has not been empirically verified. According to **Devi et al. and Jha et al. (2020)** stakeholders in the leadership and commerce disciplines are aware of NEP 2020. They additionally acknowledge that the current NEP 2020 policy emphasizes straightforward methodology over theoretical study approach, which has been used in the past. They have concluded that the leadership and commercial curricula need to be reframed in a fundamental way based on outcome-based education. Whenever a program is implemented, stakeholders must be made aware of it in order to improve its effectiveness. **Sawant et al.'s (2021)** explanation for numeracy in primary school results and low literacy as the primary objectives of NEP 2020 since research indicates that 50% of children remain struggling with basic numeracy abilities even after five decades of study in the current educational system. The three most important components of NEP 2020 have been recognized by **Kaurav et al. (2020)** pupils, language acquisition, and curriculum. They have also reported positive aspects and stakeholder perspectives regarding NEP 2020. The National Education Policy (NEP) of India represents three distinct aspects: (i) issues related to education, research, the educational organization, and schoolchildren (ii) procedure, training, truthfulness, inspiration, and information-instilling facts; and (iii) a focus on excellence, development, university, vocational, learning, and multidisciplinary learning. Preschools were shown to perform better than Anganwadi centres because they had better facilities and infrastructure.

Statement of the problem:

In this present study the researcher effort to describe the significance of early childhood care and education, pre-school education and holistic development. Therefore, the researcher considered the title of the research paper as A critical analysis of NEP2020 in school education in relation to Early Childhood Care and Education.

Objectives:

1. Role of policies and recommendations of NEP2020 imparted for ECCE.
2. Significance of an ECCE structure, skilled and capable teachers to leader, monitor, and administer Early childhood-care and Education.

Methodology:

This research paper is qualitative in nature not quantitative method. It is based on the secondary data and government documents. The study conclusion is supported by data from both primary source and secondary sources. Government documents, reports and periodicals serve as the major sources which secondary sources include journals, articles, news articles, books and websites among others. This research paper study is descriptive in nature.

Restructuring school curriculum and pedagogy:

The 10+2 curricular and pedagogical structure of the NEP 1986 has been replaced with the four-stage 5+3+3+4 structure of the NEP 2020 education policy. The first stage, known as the foundational stage (3-8), takes for five years and includes dynamic play methods and experiential learning for early childhood education. The second stage is designated as the preparation stage, and it runs for three years, from the ages of eight to eleven. During this time, pupils acquire via discovery and playing. The third stage, also referred to as the middle stage, consists of three years of learning for youngsters in the 11-14 age group using the preparatory stage's pedagogy and curriculum. In this phase, students study complex ideas in the fields of mathematics, science, and social science. humanities and other related disciplines via various educators. The secondary stage, which continues for four years and lasts from the ages of 14 to 18, is the ultimate stage. Children grow developing intellectual skills, desires for their lives, topic adaptability, deductive thinking, and comprehensive understanding throughout this fourth stage of development. Since education is given through a variety of curricular and pedagogical structure, students move away from memorizing and toward a true comprehending of the material being taught. The goal of this education is to equip students for the holistic and all-around development of an individual by nurturing not only academic but also character-building maturation.

Transforming curricular and pedagogical structure

Figure 2, New structure of school curriculum

Objective no:1

The National Education Policy 2020 of India provides various policies and guidelines for ECCE, highlighting its vital role in the entire education system. Here are several important aspects:

1. Universal Access and Early Childhood Education Centres: The National education policy 2020 seeks to ensure universal access to quality early childhood care and education for all children aged 3 to 6 by 2025. The program promotes the setting up of Anganwadis and preschools in both urban and rural settings to make sure children have access to ECCE facilities.

2. Curriculum/Pedagogy: The policy highlights the relevance of a flexible, play-based curriculum that is inclusive and developmentally beneficial to young children. It suggests incorporating early reading and numeracy skill development into enjoyable and participatory activities.

3. Teacher Training and Capacity Building: National Education Policy 2020 stresses the need for skilled and motivated educators in ECCE. It suggests measures to improve teacher training programs and provide them with the skills needed to assist with the development of young children.

It recommends collaborating with local communities, NGOs, and private organizations to provide training and support for ECCE educators.

4. Continuous assessment and monitoring: The continuous assessment and monitoring of children's progress in ECCE is recommended for ideal learning outcomes. The idea suggests creating child-friendly evaluation instruments and frameworks that are welcoming.

5. Nutrition and Health: The National education policy 2020 highlights the importance of nutrition and health in early childhood development. It promotes for the supply of nutritional meals and healthcare services in ECCE centres that foster holistic child development.

6. Parental and Community Participation: The policy emphasizes the engagement of parents and local communities in the ECCE process. It indicates awareness campaigns and outreach efforts to educate parents on the value of ECCE and their involvement in promoting children's learning.

7. Digital Integration: NEP 2020 recommends smart use of technology in ECCE to improve learning opportunities and teacher efficacy, although simultaneously emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach that encourages hands-on learning and social engagement.

Overall, NEP 2020's policies and initiatives for ECCE aim to build an adequate foundation for children's learning and development while making sure universal access to quality ECCE facilities across India. The focus on learning through play, training for educators, holistic growth, and community engagement demonstrates the policy's dedication to creating a loving environment in which young children can flourish and develop well.

Objective 2:

Early childhood care and education infrastructure, as well as skilled and qualified employees, have a significant impact on young children's development. Here are some valuable implications:

1. **Multidisciplinary Development:** Early infancy is a crucial time for brain growth and learning. Adequate facilities and qualified teachers provide conditions that promote cognitive, emotional, social, and physical growth. This wide-ranging approach assures that children build the essential abilities required for lifelong learning and success.
2. **Quality Educational Experiences:** Qualified teachers provide interesting, academically suitable educational experiences for young children. They realize the value of play-based learning, networking, and individualized care in developing imaginative thinking and ability to solve issues.
3. **Monitoring and Supervision:** ECCE-trained teachers smoothly monitor and manage children's progress and overall well-being. They may recognize developmental difficulties or delays early on and execute efficient treatments or support strategies. Early detection and intervention can greatly improve outcomes for children at risk of dropping left behind.
4. **Fostering interactions:** Early childhood educators aren't simply teachers but also caretakers who foster positive interactions with young children. These partnerships provide a firm basis for youngsters to explore their surroundings while additionally cultivating tolerance and resilience to emotion.
5. **Readiness for School and Life:** Quality early childhood education promotes academic success and lifelong learning. Children who acquire an adequate basis in their early years are better prepared for formal schooling and generally to have greater interpersonal abilities, autonomy, and intellectual potential later in life.
6. **Encourage for Families:** ECCE infrastructure may include programs to help families understand child development and parenting strategies. This assistance is critical for improving parenting skills, promoting strong parent-child interactions, and creating a supportive home environment that supplements children's learning experiences at school.
7. **Continuous Benefits:** Making investments in ECCE has proven to benefit people as well as society. They involve enhanced academic achievement, better job opportunities, decreased involvement in unlawful activity, and improved overall health.

In conclusion, an early childhood care and education infrastructure facilitated by skilled and certified instructors benefits both individual children and the community as a whole. It builds the framework for future success through promoting optimal growth, encouraging a love of learning, and assisting families in meeting their children's potential.

Suggestions:

- There is a need to establish scheduled meetings for the running of the Early Childhood Education program.
- Early Childhood Education teachers will be provided with the equipment, infrastructure, and assistance they demand.

- Early schooling differs from higher education programs. Early childhood learners are curious about things passionate, and impatient; hence, early childhood educators should be highly trained professionally.
- Early childhood educators should be properly trained in leading and handling toddlers in the development of empathetic thinking following pre-schoolers' directions, collaboration, and their own language ability.
- Concept of protection according to ECCE. The whole shape is invisible in NEP 2020 and should be clarified and given careful consideration because child care in the beginning is a crucial component of his/her general growth and development.

Conclusion:

The study suggests that the National Education Policy 2020, the first of such guidelines in the 21st century, encourages holistic development through school education, leading to overall child development. Early childhood care and education promotes play-based learning and broad education. NEP 2020 empowers learners to develop their academic programs and pathways based on their capabilities, desires, and concentration in order. It bridges the gap between curricular and extra-curricular activities, sciences and arts, and academic and professional fields to promote knowledge integration. Its Early childhood care programs for children aged 3 to 6 years can be effective in boosting student success. A child's the family atmosphere has a big impact on how they learn. Because combined families were common in the past, toddlers learned from loved ones and participated in school. At the moment, children from small homes have no chance to pursue their education. It was the school's responsibility to make sure the pupils learned. Multiple studies show that by the age of six, a child's brain has developed by 85%. Children at ECCE happily, openly, and collaboratively play with educational activities. encouraging the child's general development, then. Education committees, instructors, and philosophers have all been given access to exclusive ECCE knowledge. The new National Policy 2020 has much to say about Early Childhood Education Care, through melodies events, and seeks to offer pleasant, wonderful. Teachers employed by the centres of Anganwadi were informed of the importance of being trained in order to achieve the goal of providing ECCE education to everyone.

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